

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS IN RELATION TO SELF REGULATED LEARNING IN CUDDALORE DISTRICT

Dr. S. Kalaivani

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Annamalai University,
Annamalainagar, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Kalaivani, "Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students in Relation to Self Regulated Learning in Cuddalore District", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 236-239, 2017.

Abstract

The aim of the study is to find out the study on academic achievement of higher secondary students in relation to self regulated learning in Cuddalore District. For this purpose, a sample of 300 higher secondary students was selected through random sampling technique and normative survey method. For the present study the investigator has used the higher secondary students half-yearly examination marks as the students' academic achievement and Self-regulated learning scale (SRLS) by Dr. S. Kadiravan (1999). Results found that the higher secondary students' level of academic achievement is high and self-regulated learning is more. Findings revealed that the gender of higher secondary students is do not differ significantly in their academic achievement and type of school management of higher secondary students is differ significantly in their academic achievement. It is concluded that the gender and type of school management of higher secondary students is differ significantly in their self-regulated learning. Finding also indicated that there is negligible relationship between the self-regulated learning and academic achievement.

Key Words: Academic Achievement, Self-Regulated Learning, Gender, Type of School Management and Higher Secondary Students

Introduction:

Academic achievement is always affected the multi-dimensional correlates. The more accurate and reliable prediction of academic performance is possible only when all the achievement related variables are studied at a time. This necessitates that the different educational levels on different samples at varied places such an attempt will be of great help in arriving at worthy conclusions in respect of high level of academic achievement. According to Freeman (1969), "The achievement is concerned with the quality and quantity of learning attained in a particular subject". Travers (1955) says "It is the actual of assumed possession of knowledge that counts either for admission into a class or graduation".

According to Wood and Lerner (1938) "Education was unavoidably intellectual in which knowledge was the domination feature of educational outcomes. It is perhaps accepted basis for promotion or fulfillment or requirement for a degree". Achievement is the end product of all educational endeavour. The main concern of all educational efforts is to see that the learner achieves quality control, quality assurance and of total quality management of achievement has highly gained the attention of researches in education. The origin of the concept of self-regulation was established by the Soviet psychologists in the early 1950's and this tradition was taken up by the American psychologists. Self-regulation takes its origin from both social & cultural issues. After Bandura's social learning theory (1986), this concept has gained momentum. Self-regulation is defined as the ability to behave according to one's own intention in a flexible way (Kuhl, 1992). Social cognitive researchers have viewed self-regulation as an achievement of socialization processes (Bandura and Walters, 1963).

Need for the Study:

Learning refers to a process in which a relatively permanent change in behavioural tendency occurs as a result of reinforced practice. Learning is the basic quality of all humans. It depends on processes of perception categorization, memory and so on. Self-regulated learning refers to a cognitively inherent aspect of learning, which is constituted jointly by the complexity of information and information processing. An effective learner should be aware of the functional relations between their pattern of thoughts and actions, social and environmental outcomes. They also need to know how to use self-assessment to determine whether they are meeting their learning goals. One of the important aims of education is promoting higher order cognitive skills such as problem solving, decision making, self-evaluation, organizing and transforming information and so on. It is observed from the existing studies that these are components of academic self-regulation.

The aim of all learning is to increase the achievement level of the students. Achievement is the specified level of attainment of proficiency in academic work as evaluated by the teachers by a standardized test or by a combination of both.

Objectives of the Study:

- To assess the academic achievement of the higher secondary students.
- To measure the self-regulated learning of the higher secondary students.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between the higher secondary boys and girls in their academic achievement.

- To find out whether there is any significant difference among the government, private and aided school students in their academic achievement.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between the higher secondary boys and girls in their self-regulated learning.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference among the government, private and aided school students in their self-regulated learning.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship exists between the higher secondary students academic achievement and self-regulated learning.

Hypotheses of the Study

- The level of academic achievement of the higher secondary students is average.
- The level of self-regulated learning of the higher secondary students is average.
- There is no significant difference between the higher secondary boys and girls in their academic achievement.
- There is no significant difference among the government, private and aided school students in their academic achievement.
- There is no significant difference between the higher secondary boys and girls in their self-regulated learning.
- There is no significant difference among the government, private and aided school students in their self-regulated learning.
- There is no significant relationship exists between the higher secondary students academic achievement and self-regulated learning.

Method of the Study:

Normative survey method has been adopted for the present investigation.

Sample of the Study:

A random sample 300 students studying in 10 higher secondary schools located in Cuddalore District of Tamilnadu were selected for the study.

Scoring Procedure:

Academic achievement score was maximum marks is 1200. The investigator has classified the achievement level as follows: Below 420 is low achievement, 421-719 is average achievement and 720 and above is high achievement.

Self-regulated learning scale (SRLS) consist of 40 statements. The maximum marks is 200 and the minimum mark is 40.

Descriptive Analysis:

Hypothesis 1: The level of academic achievement of the higher secondary students is average.

Table 1: Showing the Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students

Variable	N	M	SD
Academic Achievement	300	729.85	134.59

It is evident from the Table 1, that the calculated mean score is found to be 729.85 and the standard deviation value is 134.59 respectively. Therefore hypothesis 1 is rejected and it is concluded that the level of academic achievement of the higher secondary students is high.

Hypothesis 2: The level of self-regulated learning of the higher secondary students is average.

Table 2: Showing the Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Self-Regulated Learning of Higher Secondary Students

Variable	N	M	SD
Self-Regulated Learning	300	146.27	18.05

It is evident from the Table 2, that the calculated mean score is found to be 146.27 and the standard deviation value is 18.05 respectively. Therefore hypothesis 2 is rejected and it is concluded that the self-regulated learning of the higher secondary students is more.

Differential Analysis:

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the higher secondary boys and girls in their academic achievement.

Table 3: 't' value of Academic Achievement Scores of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Gender

Variable	Sub - Samples	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance at 0.05 Level
Academic Achievement	Male	156	729.79	142.29	0.41	Not Significant
	Female	144	733.16	126.13		

The 't' value is found to be 0.41 and it is less than the table value of 1.96. It reveals that there is no significance difference between the male and female students academic achievement. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference among the government, private and aided school students in their academic achievement.

Table 4: 'F' value of Academic Achievement Scores of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Type of School Management

Variable	Source of Variance	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F	Significant
Academic Achievement	Between	1034367	2	517183.561	35.03	Significant
	Within group	4382055	297	14754.3694		
	Total	5416422	299			

A close look at table indicates that the 'F' value 35.053 of academic achievement is significant. There is significant difference between different types of higher secondary school students in their academic achievement. Since the F value is higher than the table value. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant difference between the higher secondary boys and girls in their self-regulated learning.

Table 5: 't' value of Self-Regulated Learning Scores of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Gender

Variable	Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance at 0.05 Level
Self-Regulated Learning	Male	156	144.88	17.99	1.39	Not Significant
	Female	144	147.78	18.04		

The 't' value is found to be 1.39 and it is less than the table value of 1.96. It reveals that there is no significance difference between the male and female students in respect to their self-regulated learning. Hence the null hypotheses is accepted.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant difference among the government, private and aided school students in their self-regulated learning.

Table 6: 'F' value of Self-Regulated Learning Scores of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Type of School Management

Variable	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Significant
Self-Regulated Learning	Between	1125.16	2	562.58	1.74	Not Significant
	Within group	96238.42	297	324.04		
	Total	97363.59	299			

A close look at table indicates that the 'F' value 1.74 of self-regulated learning is not significant. There is no significant difference between higher secondary students who belongs to different types of school in respect to their self-regulated learning. Since the F value is lesser than the table value. The null hypothesis is accepted.

Correlation Analysis:

Hypothesis 7: There is no significant relationship exists between the higher secondary students academic achievement and self-regulated learning.

Table 7: Showing the Correlation Values between Academic Achievement and Self-Regulated Learning of Higher Secondary Students

Variable	N	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Academic Achievement and Self-Regulated Learning	300	0.058	Not Significant

From the above table the 'r' value found to be 0.058. From this there is no significant relationship between academic achievement and self-regulated learning. Hence it is concluded that there is negligible relationship between the self-regulated learning and academic achievement.

Findings of the Study:

- The level of academic achievement of the higher secondary students is high.
- The self-regulated learning of the higher secondary students is more.
- There is no significance difference between the male and female students academic achievement.
- There is significant difference between different types of higher secondary school students in their academic achievement.
- There is no significance difference between the male and female students in respect to their self-regulated learning.

- There is no significant difference between higher secondary students who belongs to different types of school in respect to their self-regulated learning.

Conclusion:

In the present study academic achievement of higher secondary students in relation to self regulated learning in Cuddalore District. Results found that the higher secondary students' level of academic achievement is high and self-regulated learning is more and it is inferred that there is no significant relationship between academic achievement and self –regulated learning.

References:

1. Ablard, K.E., & Lipschulz, R.E. (1998). Self-regulated learning in high-achieving students: Relations to advanced reasoning, achievement, goals and gender. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90, 94-101.
2. Allen L. Edwards (1960). *Statistical analysis*, New York: Holt Rinehart and Winston.
3. Freeman, W. H.(1979). *Multiple regression and the analysis of variance and covariance*, San Francisco.
4. Guilford, J.P. (1939). *General psychology*. New York, NY: D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc.
5. Henry E. Garrett. (2006). *Statistics in Psychology and Education*, Surjeet Publication, New Delhi.
6. Kothari, C. R. (2004): *Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques (2nd Revised Edition)*, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi.
7. Visvanathan G (1996). *A Study of some Factors Associated with Academic Achievement in History of XII th Standard Pupils in Tamilnadu*, Ph.D., Edn., Annamalai University.